

HISTORICAL STAGES OF ROMAN-GERMAN LANGUAGES AND SIGNIFICANCE TODAY.

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Abstract: This article provides information about the history of the origin of the "Roman-Germanic languages", its development stages, grammatical structures, and its place in society. A discussion was held regarding the determination of its place and importance. Since language is one of the main tools that express all the cultural and scientific wealth created by mankind in the process of historical development and leave a legacy from generation to generation, we tried to approach this topic closely.

Key Words: Romance languages, Romanus, dead languages, Germanic languages, official language.

Introduction: Romanic languages belong to the Indo-European language family, forming a group of related languages that all evolved from Latin, sharing common development patterns and many similar elements in their structure. The term "Roman" (from Latin *romanus*, meaning "belonging to Rome" or "related to the Roman Empire") was first used in the early Middle Ages to refer to the vernacular languages, which were distinct from classical Latin and Germanic dialects. In Spain and Italy, Romanic languages are also known as "New Latin languages." These languages are spoken in over 60 countries (e.g., French in 30 countries, Spanish in 20, Portuguese in 7, and Italian in 3), with more than 600 million speakers.

The following languages belong to the Romanic group:

- a) French - Spoken by about 60 million people, it is the official language of France (capital: Paris);
- b) Italian - Spoken by nearly 50 million people, it is the official language of Italy (capital: Rome);
- c) Spanish - Spoken by approximately 95 million people, it is the official language of Spain (capital: Madrid);
- d) Portuguese - Spoken by over 45 million people, it is the official language of Portugal (capital: Lisbon);
- e) Romanian - Spoken by nearly 18 million people, it is the official language of

Romania (capital: Bucharest);

f) Moldovan - Spoken by nearly 2 million people, it is the official language of Moldova (capital: Chişinău);

g) Provençal - Spoken by over 10 million people, primarily in the southeastern part of France; h) Sardinian - Spoken by over 1 million people, primarily on the island of Sardinia, Italy;

i) Catalan - Spoken by over 5 million people, mainly in Spain;

j) Rhaeto-Romanic - Spoken by 550 thousand people, mostly in Italy.

Dead languages such as Latin, Oscan, and Umbrian also belong to the Romanic group. There is no consensus in linguistics on the exact number of Romanic languages. According to current data, there are typically considered to be 12 major ones: Spanish, Galician, Portuguese, Catalan, Occitan (Provençal), French, Italian, Sardinian, Rhaeto-Romanic, Romanian, Moldovan, and Dalmatian (considered extinct since the 19th century). The uneven development of Romanic languages complicates their classification and exact count.

The distribution of Romanic languages is divided into three regions:

1. Old Romania - The part of Europe that was part of the Roman Empire and retained Romance languages, including Italy, Portugal, most of Spain, France, southern Belgium, western and southern Switzerland, Romania, and Moldova, as well as parts of northern Greece and Macedonia.
2. New Romania - Areas outside Europe where Romance-speaking populations emerged as a result of colonialism in the 16th-18th centuries, such as Canada, Mexico, Central America, South America, and the Antilles.
3. Colonial regions - Areas where Romance languages became official alongside local languages due to colonial policies, such as much of Africa, South Asia, and smaller regions in Oceania.

Romanic languages are the result of the gradual evolution of the vulgar Latin spoken in the territories of the Roman Empire. Their development can be divided into four stages:

1. 3rd century BCE to 5th century CE - The Romanization period, during which local languages were replaced by vulgar Latin. Differences between the future Romance languages began to emerge.
2. 5th to 9th centuries - The period of the fragmentation of the Roman Empire and the formation of barbarian kingdoms. Romance languages were influenced by superstrata elements (such as Germanic invasions by the Visigoths, Franks, Burgundians, Lombards, etc.), leading to distinct developments in these languages.

3. 10th to 16th centuries - The period of the development of writing in Romance languages and the expansion of their social functions. Early written texts appeared in French in the 9th century, in Italian and Spanish in the 10th century, in Provençal, Catalan, and Sardinian in the 11th century, in Portuguese and Galician in the 12th century, in Rhaeto-Romanic in the 14th century, and in Romanian in the 16th century. Literary languages began to emerge from dialects.

4. 16th to 19th centuries - The period of the formation, standardization, and enrichment of national languages. The development of Romance languages was uneven: some languages became national languages early on and later gained international importance (e.g., French and Spanish), while others lost their significance in the Middle Ages and regained literary status in the 19th-20th centuries (e.g., Provençal, Catalan). In areas outside Europe, local variants of Romance languages developed (e.g., Canadian French, Brazilian Portuguese, and various forms of Spanish in Central and South America).

Germanic languages are another group in the Indo-European family. These languages are widely spoken in Western Europe, including in countries like the United Kingdom, Germany, Austria, the Netherlands, Belgium, Switzerland, Luxembourg, Denmark, Norway, Iceland, as well as in North America, South Africa, Australia, New Zealand, and parts of Asia (e.g., India, Pakistan). Around 550 million people speak Germanic languages.

The following languages belong to the Germanic language group:

a) English - Spoken by 400 million people. It is spoken in the United Kingdom, Iceland, the United States, Canada, the South American Union, and other places. English is the official language in several countries, including the United Kingdom, the United States, and Canada.

b) German - Spoken by over 100 million people. It is the official language of the Federal Republic of Germany and the Republic of Austria.

c) Danish - Spoken by nearly 4 million people. It is the official language of Denmark.

d) Swedish - Spoken by over 7 million people. It is the official language of Sweden. e) Norwegian - Spoken by 3.5 million people. It is the official language of Norway.

f) Dutch - Spoken by 13 million people. It is the official language of the Netherlands.

g) Icelandic - Spoken by 250,000 people. It is the official language of Iceland.

The extinct languages of the Visigothic and Ostrogothic languages also belong to the Germanic language group. The Germanic languages are divided into three

smaller groups: Northern, Western, and Eastern. The national German languages are made up of tribal dialects. The Germanic tribes were initially located in the southern part of the Scandinavian Peninsula, the Jutland Peninsula, and the Schleswig-Holstein region. The ancient Germanic dialects were divided into northern and southern groups. In the 2nd and 1st centuries BCE, some Germanic tribes migrated from Scandinavia to the Baltic region, forming the Eastern Germanic group. Based on the northern Scandinavian dialects, the Swedish and Danish languages later developed, while the Norwegian language emerged from the western Scandinavian dialects. In the 19th and 20th centuries, the migration of people from Norway to Iceland and the Faroe Islands led to the development of the Norwegian and Faroese languages. Yiddish, a later representative of the Indo-European languages, developed in the 10th-14th centuries from Upper German dialects with influences from Semitic and, later, Slavic languages. The Afrikaans language arose from the combination of Dutch dialects with English, German, French, and some African and Malay-Portuguese languages.

Germanic languages are also distinguished by their complex grammar and phonetics, often having unique features in word structure and pronunciation. In the current German phonological system, monophthongs and diphthongs make up 45% (16 vowel phonemes and 3 diphthongs); the consonant system consists of 18 consonant phonemes and 2 affricate sounds. All phonemes differ in terms of their place of articulation, method, and pronunciation. The grammatical structure is distinguished by both analytic and synthetic characteristics. For example, gender and case forms in nouns are primarily expressed analytically, while number categories are expressed synthetically. This pattern is also observed in the forms of other parts of speech. The system of word formation is well-developed; compounding is widely used to form nouns (mainly technical terms). The vocabulary includes many words borrowed from Latin, French, Italian, English, and other languages, and the writing system is based on the Latin alphabet.

One of the achievements of the Romanic-Germanic language family is the elevation of the English language to the status of a "global language." One reason for this is that English is easier to learn compared to other languages and is widely spread across the world. Moreover, many information resources are also available in this language.

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